

TOWARDS REAL-TIME AURALIZATION ON FPGAS

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ABSTRACT

Auralization seeks to reproduce the acoustical properties of a space through artificial reverberation (typically implemented as a room impulse response convolution). This process is computationally intensive, especially for long Impulse Responses (IRs). While CPUs and GPUs (to lesser extents) have been broadly used for auralization, the potential of Field-Programmable Gate Arrays (FPGAs) remains largely unexplored. This paper investigates FPGA-based real-time convolution for auralization purposes, leveraging High-Level Synthesis (HLS) and the Syfala toolchain to implement two convolution techniques: a time-domain uniformly partitioned overlap-save (TUPOLS) algorithm and a frequency-domain uniformly partitioned overlap-save (FUPOLS) algorithm. These findings highlight the potential of FPGA-based auralization and suggest avenues for further optimization.

1. INTRODUCTION

Auralization aims at artificially recreating the acoustic characteristics of an environment. It is the process of rendering the sound field of a source in a space, in such a way as to simulate the listening experience at a given position in the modeled space [1]. Auralization has many applications in various fields, including immersive concerts, Virtual Reality (VR), etc. It is generally implemented by convolving the Impulse Response (IR) of a modeled or measured space with an input audio signal. The computational cost of a convolution increases with the length of the IR. In some cases (e.g., large churches, etc.), the IR can be longer than 10 seconds, which corresponds to an FIR filter with hundreds of thousands of coefficients. Many algorithms have been developed to overcome this issue and are known as Fast Convolution methods.

Most convolution implementations are based on CPU architectures [2], but some projects also rely on GPUs [3]. In this paper, we study the implementation of these algorithms on Field Programmable Gate Arrays (FPGAs). FPGAs are often referred to as *programmable circuits*. They offer exceptional latency performances for real-time audio signal processing [4, 5] and they can be used to manage a large number of audio channels in parallel at a very low cost [6]. FPGA architectures are particularly well suited

for parallelizing computations and processing streams of data, making them a good fit for applications around auralization.

Only few attempts have been made to implement auralization algorithms on FPGAs. A reason for this might be that implementing complex audio DSP algorithms on an FPGA is a notoriously hard task. The use of Hardware Description Languages (HDL) such as Verilog and VHDL requires advanced hardware skills and is out of reach for many audio programmers.

This article presents auralization algorithms that are adapted to FPGA architectures, using the Syfala toolchain [7], which relies on High Level Synthesis (HLS) to compile C code down to FPGA. Hence, all implementations developed here are based on Fast Convolution techniques and are written in C. We study in particular a time domain algorithm and a frequency domain algorithm and show that much better performance can be obtained from the frequency domain algorithm.

Section 2 presents the state-of-the-art. Sections 3 and 4 respectively describe our time and frequency domain implementations. Section 5 introduces hardware optimization techniques used in our solution. Section 6 presents the performance of both implementations. Finally, Sections 7 and 8 provide an overview of the more general context in which this work was carried out as well as ongoing and future works around this project.

2. STATE OF THE ART AND PROBLEM STATEMENT

First works around auralization date back to the 1960s. At the time, geometrical approaches such as ray tracing [8] or image source techniques [9] were developed to cope with the limited computational resources available. In the 1990s, the first sound field simulations based on physical wave equations [10] were conducted. The rise of GPUs in the 2010s allowed for the solving of these wave-based equations in real-time [11, 12]. Recently, Machine Learning and data-driven methods started to be explored [13, 14], but efficient fast convolution techniques are still currently the main approach for real-time auralization [2, 15].

Partitioned convolution techniques were first introduced by Kulp [16] in the late 1980s and later improved by Egelmeers and al. and Gardner [17–19]. These techniques decompose the IR and the input signal in smaller blocks of samples. "Sub-convolutions" are then computed between the IR blocks and the input signal blocks to deliver partial outputs. In these methods, the input signal blocks al-

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Figure 1. Time-domain Uniformly Partitioned Overlap-Save algorithm (TUPOLS) with P blocks of B samples.

ways have the same length, because the input signal cannot be predicted. Partitioned convolution can be implemented using equal or different length for IR blocks, leading to uniformly-partitioned [2, 16] or non-uniformly partitioned convolution [2, 18]. Thanks to the FFT algorithm [20], it is more efficient to compute convolutions in the frequency domain [2, 21, 22] by multiplying FFT results and then performing an inverse FFT.

Partitioned convolution and FFT-based convolutions can be combined, leading to highly efficient convolution techniques. It has been shown that for high order FIR filters, non-uniformly partitioned FFT-based convolutions are more efficient [2, 18]. They are the current state of the art for computing convolutions for real-time audio signal processing applications on CPUs.

While a lot of research has been conducted on FPGA-based 2D convolutions for image processing and Deep Learning [15, 23, 24], fewer works were carried on FPGA-based 1D convolution for audio purposes. The computation of FFTs on FPGAs can be tedious, and the possibility of parallelization might give an advantage to direct convolutions. Thus, direct convolutions and FFT-based convolutions are relevant on FPGAs.

In 2009, [25] implemented direct convolutions on FPGAs, and in 2015, [26] implemented FFT-based overlap-save convolutions on FPGA for digital pulse compression. Both approaches are tested in this article. Other approaches such as modal-based techniques may be relevant for FPGAs [27]. The modal approach focuses on implementing resonance modes of a room. A drawback is that it is a destructive approach as only a limited number of modes can be implemented and efficiently extracting mode parameters from an impulse response remains a complicated and approximate task [28].

As for other platforms, partitioned convolution methods

are significantly more efficient on FPGAs than other techniques. Non-Uniformly partitioned convolutions are difficult to implement because they need appropriate computation scheduling in order to deliver the correct output. Moreover, the choice of IR partition is itself a complicated problem. For those reasons, only uniformly partitioned convolutions have been evaluated in this paper.

Partitioned convolutions rely on *Overlap-Save* (OLS) or *Overlap-Add* (OLA) schemes [2, 29]. Indeed, the segmentation of the input signal leads to sub-convolutions whose outputs are overlapping and therefore need to be properly delayed and summed. OLS allows to directly get the right output block while storing redundant input blocks instead of storing sub-convolutions results and sum them. OLS saves one addition for overlapping samples, so it is usually preferred to OLA. In regard to these prior points, OLA is not considered in this paper and the two algorithms studied here are referred to as TUPOLS (Time-domain Uniformly Partitioned Overlap-Save) and FUPOLS (Frequency-domain Uniformly Partitioned Overlap-Save).

3. TIME DOMAIN APPROACH

The TUPOLS algorithm is depicted in Figure 1. It is based on a temporal transcription of the Uniformly Partitioned OLS technique presented in [2]. The *sub-convolutions* are computed in the time domain using direct (or linear) convolution. Staying in the time domain saves the computation of DFTs and the use of complex numbers, which are twice as heavy to process as real numbers. The IR and the input block are decomposed in P Blocks of B samples. The input block length does not have to match the IR block length for TUPOLS algorithms (even though we do it here for simplicity). Input blocks are stored in a time do-

Figure 2. Frequency-domain Uniformly Partitioned Overlap-Save (FUPOLS) algorithm [2].

main delay-line delaying the blocks of B samples at each iteration of the algorithm.

The convolution is decomposed in P small $B \times B$ linear sub-convolutions, however in order to avoid a side effect of the block decomposition at frontiers of blocks, current input blocks x_n and x_{n-1} are concatenated (this is the OLS principle [2, 29]) and successively convolved with IR blocks h_i with $i \in \{0, 1, \dots, P - 1\}$ of size B .

The result of the sub-convolution is of length $3B - 1$, but due to OLS we only need the samples between B and $2B$. Thus, we are able to not calculate the entire output of the sub-convolutions but only the right B samples. Sub-convolutions are then summed together to obtain the corresponding output block.

4. FREQUENCY DOMAIN APPROACH

The FUPOLS algorithm is adapted from [2] and shown in Figure 2. It is based on the same principles as the TUPOLS algorithm, but transposed in the frequency domain. It uses circular convolutions instead of linear convolutions. As for TUPOLS, the IR is partitioned in P subfilters of B samples, and the input blocks are of length B samples as well. Input blocks x_n and x_{n-1} are concatenated in a buffer window. Then, a $2B$ -length DFT is performed on these blocks, and only the first $B + 1$ coefficients are kept since we only manipulate real data.

These $B + 1$ coefficients are then put in the delay-line (sometimes called *frequency-domain delay-line*), which is performing a shift of $B + 1$ samples at each iteration of the algorithm. The P subfilters are zero-padded with B zeros, and then a $2B$ -length DFT is performed and only the first $B + 1$ coefficients are kept just like for the input blocks. This process can be done offline, since the

IR does not change between two iterations. Both input blocks and subfilter spectrum are then multiplied, which is sometimes called “spectral convolution” [?]. The results are then summed in the frequency domain. $B - 1$ complex conjugate coefficients are concatenated to the sum of spectral convolutions and a $2B$ -point inverse DFT is computed. Since the DFT lengths are inferior to the length of the output result ($2B < 3B - 1$), the first $B-1$ samples are time-aliased, but this is not a problem since we are only interested in the last B samples (due to OLS). The first B samples are therefore discarded and the last B samples are returned as the output block.

A key parameter of this algorithm is the block length B , which is also defining the DFT length $K = 2B$. This transform length is the minimal length that guarantees the last B valid samples. Most FFTs are more efficient on power of two, so the block length must be a power of two as well.

5. HARDWARE OPTIMIZATIONS

The FPGA architecture offers several possibilities of hardware acceleration for computations. On the other hand, they are limited in memory and computing resources. The Syfala toolchain relies on VITIS HLS which is the HLS tool provided by AMD/Xilinx (see §1). It provides directives and pragmas to guide hardware design and synthesis [30]. In this section, we discuss the hardware optimization performed during the implementation of the algorithms. Both TUPOLS and FUPOLS algorithms are implemented on a AMD/Xilinx DIGILENT Zybo Z7-20 board.

5.1 Memory Constraints

The AMD/Xilinx Zynq-7000 FPGA used inside the Digilent Zybo Z7-20 board has limited memory resources. It is impossible to store more than approximately 35,000 real coefficients on the Programmable Logic (PL) Block RAMs (BRAM) [31]. Since we want the IR to last several seconds, both the IR coefficients and the input delay-line (whose length is the same as that of the IR) are stored in the DDR external memory and implemented as ring buffers.

FPGAs can retrieve several items in a single memory access request, which is called *bursting*. In order to obtain the best possible burst (approximately one data read per cycle), the IR and the input data should be stored contiguously in memory in such a way that they are accessed in the ascending order. This is depicted in Figure 3 for the TUPOLS case.

For each algorithm iteration, a new input signal block is written below the most recent blocks. The IR blocks are written in memory at the initialization of the algorithm. In this way, the data is read in the ascending order (from the newest to the oldest block for the input signal (block n to 0 in Figure 3), and from the first block, to the last block (block 0 to $P-1$) for the IR). The number of bursted data should always be even. Thanks to bursts and pipelining (explained below), a new data can be obtained at every clock cycle.

Figure 3. Data structure in memory for optimizing burst access (TUPOLS case).

5.2 Dataflow Pipeline

One advantage of FPGAs is that they can process streams of data. In particular, it is possible to “pipeline” function calls to improve the overall throughput. This is referred to as “dataflow mode” in AMD/Xilinx tools. Dataflow demands particular code architecture but offers significant latency gains. It is typically suited to read-compute-write code structures, which is the case here. Dataflow partly overcomes the bottleneck of reading the data from the external memory, because it allows the computing step to start as soon as the first blocks of data are available.

5.3 Numerical Formats

Most audio programs compute data in floating point format. However, for specific hardware like FPGAs, fixed point format is more efficient and consumes less power and hardware resources [32]. The precision is not the same for both formats: the dynamic range of fixed-point numbers is smaller and thus it is required to manually adapt the precision throughout the calculation, which is a difficult task for non-expert programmers. Numerous tests have been conducted on both TUPOLS and FUPOLS algorithms to maximize the computational efficiency while keeping an acceptable noise. The fixed-point arithmetic can be implemented for TUPOLS algorithm without too much complexity, but the computation of fixed-point FFTs can be tedious because of overflows occurring at different stages of computation [33]. Moreover, it was observed that the AMD/Xilinx HLS tools did not always take advantage of the use of fixed-point arithmetic in terms of resources and latency, leading to similar results as floating-point arithmetic with a poorer precision. For those reasons, floating-point arithmetic was preferred in our implementation.

5.4 Loop Nest Pipeline

The TUPOLS algorithm is using linear convolution decomposed in sub-convolutions. The corresponding code is made out of two nested loops. The outer loop is iterating over the samples of the block while the inner loop is multiplying the B coefficients to get one output sample. It was observed that interchanging the loops – i.e. setting the outer loop for the accumulation and the inner loop for processing each samples – could give significant gains in terms of computation throughput, because it removes the memory dependency in the inner loop [4]. The loop responsible for multiplying coefficients being the outer loop, we are able to unroll the new inner loop because the IR coefficients array is now constant in this loop. This enables Xilinx HLS tool to optimize the first loop pipelining and get much better performance. With this optimization, the design latency¹ is divided by factors going up to 350.

5.5 FFT-based Convolution

The FUPOLS algorithm uses circular convolution, that is, using the FFT algorithm. Numerous implementations of FFT exist on several platforms.

It was chosen to use AMD/Xilinx’ LOGICORE IP FFT provided in VITIS HLS [33]. This is a C/C++ library adaptation of Xilinx FFT IP based on Cooley-Tuckey FFT algorithm [20]. This library was used for simplicity, because it is one of the only libraries adapted to HLS. However, its use remains complex and several implementation constraints must be considered. In particular, to use floating point arithmetic in LOGICORE IP FFT in VITIS HLS, it is necessary to set bitwidth to 32 bits, choose 24 or 25 bits phase factors, dynamically set the FFT length, and choose

¹ Design latency is the time it takes for a design to be executed on the FPGA. It does not impact the overall audio latency of the system. Throughout this paper, we refer to “design latency” as “latency” as we never talk about audio latency.

Figure 4. TUPOLS and FUPOLS CSIM outputs compared to the MATLAB convolution implementation

the Radix-2 burst I/O architecture [33], which is not the optimal one in terms of latency.

6. RESULTS

The previously discussed TUPOLS and FUPOLS algorithms were submitted to a broad range of tests. The correctness of the output signal was verified and then their performance was evaluated. Figure 4 show the comparison to the MATLAB standard convolution function in floating point data. The Root-mean Squared Error for TUPOLS and FUPOLS was calculated :

$$RMSE_{TUPOLS_{float}} = 1.0654 \times 10^{-05} \quad (1)$$

$$RMSE_{FUPOLS_{float}} = 4.2312 \times 10^{-07} \quad (2)$$

Errors between MATLAB implementation and TUPOLS and FUPOLS algorithms are acceptable considering floating point format, though FUPOLS show better performances : for long signals, optimised FFTs can accumulate less errors. In both cases, the difference between signals is not audible. To evaluate performance, we focus on two main indicators: input-output latency and FPGA resource usage, evaluated by the AMD/Xilinx compilation tools during synthesis. Estimated resource and latency during implementation can vary a bit compared to synthesis. Input-output latency is measured in clock cycles (the internal Zybo Z7-20 clock is set to 125 MHz [31]) and resources are presented in percentage relative to the maximum available on the board. Only floating point results are shown here and a sampling rate of $f_s = 48$ kHz is used.

6.1 TUPOLS Performances

For the time domain approach TUPOLS, Figure 5 shows the I/O latency per output samples for several IR lengths, going from 1 to 5 seconds, and for several input block lengths. Resources do not evolve with the length of the IR because the sub-convolutions are implemented sequentially, but they do with block length. Figure 6 shows the resources consumption for different input block lengths for a one second IR.

On Figure 5, we observe that the TUPOLS algorithm is only able to deliver the output signal in real-time only for

Figure 5. TUPOLS latency in function of IR length. The dashed line represent the maximum possible latency, over this line two successive convolutions will overlap in time.

Figure 6. TUPOLS resources on a Zybo-Z7-20 as a function of input block length for a 1s IR. The dashed line represents 100% of resources.

IR inferior to 1 second with long block length. However Figure 6 shows that resource consumption grows with the block length. Hence, a convolution with an IR of 1 second cannot be executed on the Zybo Z7-20 with TUPOLS. This is mostly due to the unrolling of loops during the sub-convolutions computation. The majority of the latency and resources consumption is still due to the computation of linear convolutions despite hardware and software optimizations discussed above. It is clear that the Zybo Z7-20 is not dimensioned to support such calculations with real-time constraints. Better performance could be achieved with a bigger FPGA. However, this would not help with the bottleneck shown in Figure 5 (i.e., latency limitation due to memory accesses) unless it contains enough block RAM to store the whole IR and the delay-line.

6.2 FUPOLS Performances

FUPOLS algorithm provides much better performances. Figure 7 shows the I/O latency per output sample for several IR lengths going from 1 to 10 seconds for several input block lengths. As for the TUPOLS algorithm, resources do not increase with the length of the IR because processing is carried out sequentially. Figure 8 shows the resource consumption for different input block lengths for a 1 second IR.

The I/O latency of the FUPOLS algorithm is below the

Figure 7. FUPOLS latency in function of the IR length (floating point data). The dashed line represent the maximum possible latency.

Figure 8. FUPOLS resources on a Zybo-Z7-20 as a function of the input block length.

real-time maximum for IRs going up to more than 10 seconds, depending on the block length. All resources are acceptable (below 70%). A notable difference with TUPOLS is that resource don't evolve a lot with the block length (only BRAMs change at 1024 samples block length, due to FFT LOGICORE IP configuration). This is because the spectral convolution computations are only pipelined and not unrolled. The resources consumption is mainly due to FFT computations.

6.3 Algorithms Comparison

TUPOLS and FUPOLS algorithms have quite distinct performances. TUPOLS algorithm is below real-time requirements. The bottleneck is the direct convolutions in terms of resources and latency. A bigger FPGA with more DSPs or LUTs could solve the problem of resource consumption, but the latency is still beyond real-time for IRs superior to 1 second. Despite the loop inversion and dual-ports BRAM on the Zybo Z7-20, the VITIS HLS compiler was not able to remove all memory dependencies, leading to poor pipeline performance [30].

The FUPOLS algorithm has significantly better performances. The resource consumption is reasonable for the Zybo Z7-20 and does not evolve with block length or IR length. It is thus possible to implement convolution with long IRs (several seconds) in real-time. The limitation only comes from the latency, again related to memory ac-

cesses, but acceptable up to 10 second IR length. The better performance of FUPOLS can be explained by the lower complexity of FFT-based convolution ($O(\log N)$ per output sample for FFT-based, $O(N)$ for direct convolution), but also by a better use of VITIS HLS dataflow mode and bursts in memory accesses. The bottleneck of this algorithm is still the spectral convolutions and the DFT computation, but it is closely followed by memory access limitations. FPGAs with more memory resources having a faster DFT implementation could be relevant here.

7. FUTURE WORKS

As mentioned in §1, FPGAs are a good fit for spatial audio applications as they can manage a large number of audio channels in parallel. This has been demonstrated in [6] where various audio interfaces targeting FPGAs and providing hundreds of audio inputs and outputs were introduced. The work presented in this paper can be seen as a first milestone towards running multichannel convolution operations in the context of spatial audio for advanced auralization applications. Much work remains to be done though for deploying spatial audio algorithms such as ambisonics decoder [34] on an FPGA. The use of much larger FPGAs than the ones present on the Zybo Z7-20 will be essential to provide the necessary additional computational power. We are also in the process of investigating the use of other auralization techniques such as modal reverberation as an alternative to the convolution implementations presented here. The parallel nature of FPGAs could be exploited in this context to compute a large number of modal filters in parallel. We recently proposed a paper (under review) comparing the performances of CPUs, FPGAs, and GPUs for this kind of applications [35].

8. CONCLUSION

In this paper, we investigated the implementation of various convolution techniques on an FPGA aiming convolution-based artificial reverberation and hence auralization applications. Similar tendencies can be observed between FPGA and CPUs in this context: for long IRs, FFT-based convolution is more efficient, despite the possibility of hardware optimization offered by FPGAs. Fixed-point arithmetic could potentially improve these results but is tedious to implement in HLS with the use of external libraries. This is where we experienced the limitation of the HLS approach: further hardware optimizations would probably require a low-level VHDL or Verilog implementation, which is out of reach for now.

“Real-world” auralization applications imply the processing of a large number of audio channels in parallel using convolutions and will necessitate the use of a large FPGA. Dynamic IRs have not been investigated here, however auralization would benefit from it. Further software implementations have been discarded for this study, but could be of interest:

- Non-uniformly partitioned convolution which is theoretically more efficient than uniformly partitioned

convolution on CPUs could benefit from FPGA hardware in terms of computational load.

- The use of NTTs (Number Theoretic Transforms) to replace FFTs for circular convolutions. Currently not relevant on CPUs compared to efficient implementation of FFTs [2], NTTs could be particularly well suited to embedded hardware like FPGAs and fixed-point arithmetic. Important resources and latency gains could be observed.

More generally, we believe that FPGAs will help improve auralization systems targeting general public applications.

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